

Studies on combining ability and heterosis in rice

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The usefulness of a particular cross in the exploitation of heterosis in rice is judged by analyzing combining ability. An attempt was made to understand the nature of gene action governing grain yield in heterotic F_1 rice combinations at the Directorate of Rice Research in Hyderabad, India.

For this study, we used 33 genotypes as male parents to make 99 crosses with three cytoplasmic male sterile lines—V20A, IR58025A, and IR62829A—in a line \times tester mating design. The 138 treatments of 99 F_1 s of 3 lines, 33 testers, and 2 traditional varieties—Jaya and Rasi—were laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications in the 1992 dry season (DS). Each treatment (plot) consisted of one row of 15 plants, with one plant hill⁻¹ and 20 \times 15-cm spacing. Five plants from each plot were randomly measured for yield and yield component analysis.

Analysis of variance indicated that differences among treatments, which included 36 parents and 99 hybrids, were highly significant for all characters studied, implying a high degree of genetic differences in the material.

In general, variance due to specific combining ability (SCA) was greater than that due to general combining ability (GCA) for the characters studied, indicating the predominance of nonadditive gene interaction in governing yield and other related traits. This offers the possibility of exploiting heterosis.

Of the 99 F_1 s, 21 cross combinations exhibited >20% yield advantage over the best check Jaya. The table presents the performance, SCA effects of crosses, GCA effects of parents, and standard

Yield performance, SCA effects of crosses, GCA effects of parents, and standard heterosis in heterotic hybrid combinations identified, 1992 dry season.^a

Code	Cross combination	Yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	SCA effect	GCA effect of female	GCA effect of male	Standard heterosis (over Jaya)
A1/R31	IR58025A/Suweon 287 R	27.8	6.63**	1.46**H	4.96**H	75.9**
A3/R15	IR62829A/Chianung Senyu	26.7	5.84**	-0.13 A	6.21**H	68.4**
A3/R26	IR62829A/Mahsuri	25.7	11.17**	-0.13 A	-0.11 A	62.8**
A2/R5	IR58025A/IR46R	24.0	2.71*	1.46**H	5.11**A	51.8**
A2/R17	IR58025A/Suweon 318R	24.0	4.94**	1.46**H	2.88**H	51.8**
A2/R28	IR58025A/ARC11353R	23.0	4.88**	1.46**	1.94 A	45.6**
A1/R30	V20A/UPR254-85-ITCA	22.6	6.75**	-1.33**L	2.41**H	42.4**
A2/R2	IR58025A/IR9761-19-1R	22.4	1.49 ns	1.46**H	4.66**H	41.1**
A3/R4	IR62829A/Vajram R	22.3	2.69*	-0.13 A	4.91**H	40.8**
A3/R9	IR58025A/IR28178-70-2-3R	21.9	2.33 ns	1.46**H	3.36**H	38.7**
A1/R22	V20A/IR2797-125	21.8	3.46**	-1.33**L	4.78**H	37.9**
A2/R32	IR58025A/HKR119	20.9	2.63*	1.46**H	2.15 A	32.3**
A3/R11	IR62829A/IR35366-40-3-3R	20.8	4.67**	-0.13 A	1.54 A	31.6**
A3/R7	IR62829A/IR13419-13-1R	20.5	1.90 ns	-0.13 A	3.96**H	29.8**
A2/R15	IR58025A/Chianung Senyu	20.4	-1.95 ns	1.46**H	6.21**H	29.1**
A2/R14	IR58025A/IET9311	20.3	2.50*	1.46**H	1.61 A	28.6**
A1/R5	V20A/IR46R	19.7	1.17*	-1.33**L	5.11**H	24.7**
A1/R4	V20A/Vajram R	19.6	1.24 ns	-1.33**L	4.94**H	24.2**
A2/R7	IR58025A/IR13419-13-1R	19.6	-0.60 ns	1.46**	3.96**H	23.8**
A1/R18	V20A/IR1361R	19.2	4.78**	-1.33**L	0.96 A	21.5**
A1/R2	V20A/IR9761-19-1R	19.0	0.95 ns	-1.33**L	4.66**H	20.3**

** , * = significant at 1 and 5% level, respectively; ns = not significant, H = high GCA effects, A = average, L = low GCA effects.

heterosis over Jaya. Thirteen of these 21 superior crosses exhibited significant SCA effects. The other eight crosses registered nonsignificant SCA effects. The cross A3/R26 had very high SCA effects but did not rank high in yield. On the other hand, crosses A2/R31 and A3/R15 showed a very high mean yield performance with moderately significant SCA effects. Crosses with nonsignificant SCA effects performed better than some crosses with significant SCA effects (such as A2/R31, A3/R11, A2/R14, A2/R18, etc.).

These results clearly indicated that high-yielding hybrids need not be the ones with high SCA effects and vice versa as reported earlier.

Results showed that of 13 crosses with significant SCA effects, 10 crosses involved one parent with high GCA effects and others had either high, average, or low combining ability effects (see table). This indicates additive as well as nonadditive genetic interactions operating in the crosses studied. ■

Breeding methods — tissue culture

Effects of L-tryptophan, L-proline, and activated charcoal on plant regeneration in indica rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Production and maintenance of embryogenic calli and subsequent plant regeneration in higher frequency

are important aspects of tissue culture. A rapid decrease in morphogenetic capacity with age in culture has often been observed. To overcome this problem, several methods have been suggested. We report the promotive effect of L-tryptophan, L-proline, and activated charcoal on plant regeneration in long-term callus cultures of indica rice.

Callus cultures were raised from 4-d-old coleoptile tissue of indica rice (*Oryza sativa* L. cv Kasturi). Mature